

a. Plant height groups of 370 varieties released during post-IR8 era (1967–79). b. Ratio of 275 semidwarf varieties released during post-IR8 era that were developed at IRR1 or in national programs (local). c. Sources of the dwarf genes in 183 locally developed rices released during the post-IR8 era. d. Sources of the dwarf genes in the ancestors of 38 local semidwarfs used as parents in varieties released in the post-IR8 era. e. Sources of the dwarf genes in the ancestors of 6 local semidwarfs. f. DGWG, the semidwarf gene-source for almost all semidwarf varieties.

semidwarf varieties were themselves progeny of locally developed semidwarfs.

We traced the parentage of the 2d-generation semidwarf parents and found that 47% were direct progeny of TNI and 40%, of IR8 (figure, D). But 16% were progeny of still earlier crosses made with local semidwarfs.

Traced back a 3d generation (figure, E), 50% of the local semidwarfs were progeny of TNI, 17% of IR8. A third of them were direct progeny of crosses made with DGWG.

The pattern we found substantiates earlier findings based on analysis of breeding records. TNI was developed in Taiwan from a cross involving DGWG. TNI was first grown by some farmers around 1956 and was officially released in 1960. IRR1 scientists in 1962 crossed DGWG and Peta to give IR8, released in late 1966.

National rice breeders first adopted TNI as a source of semidwarfism in their hybridizations. When IR8 became

available, many breeders dropped TNI and adopted IR8 as a parent.

Although DGWG is four generations removed in some local semidwarfs, it is the ultimate dwarfism source of almost all the semidwarf rice varieties outside

mainland China.

DGWG is thought to have originated in Taiwan or in Fujian, China. Dr. T. T. Chang, IRR1 geneticist, brought DGWG and other semidwarf gene sources to IRR1 in 1961. ■

MTU 6024 – a high yielding variety tolerant of the brown planthopper

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MTU 6024 is a dwarf selection from the cross IR8/SLO 13, developed at Maruteru ARS, West Godavari. It was identified in the F₅ during 1974 kharif (May–Nov). The cultivar is weakly sensitive to photoperiod with 140 days maturity in

early kharif. It tillers moderately, and has dark green leaves, late senescence, seed dormancy at maturity, and long, bold grain without white belly. It is tolerant of bacterial blight and brown planthopper.

With 40 kg N/ha, MTU 6024 yielded 6.1 t/ha – significantly higher than the medium-duration variety Prabhat (5.2 t/ha) in early 1976 kharif.

MTU 6024 is now in large-scale testing. Farmers like it for its high yield, high milling recovery (75%), and excellent cooking quality. It was planted on an estimated 25,000 ha on the Godavari western delta alone in the early 1979 kharif. ■